

Co-designing opportunities towards the development of Irish offshore wind

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Executive Summary:

This study aims to review relevant blueprints, visions and masterplans for offshore wind development in other countries, in order to inform a methodology for writing a blueprint, arising from the research conducted in the Eirwind project. The Eirwind Blueprint is envisaged as a synthesis of the studies conducted through Eirwind, ultimately presented, such that policy makers may derive value for forward (master) planning purposes.

Three case studies have been selected to cover a range of issues, including infrastructure, government supports, innovation and public engagement, from New York and Virginia in the United States, and Taiwan. The blueprint process and resulting masterplan for New York consists of a comprehensive suite of actions for site selection, grid development, economic supports and stakeholder engagement. The vision for Virginia outlines infrastructure and geographical advantages, and the opportunity for Virginia to become a hub for the East Coast offshore wind supply chain.. The Taiwan government's promotion targets, strategies and incentives for offshore wind including the "Thousand Wind Turbines" project, Feed-in-Tariff, and incentives for demonstration projects have effectively supported the offshore wind industry in that country. The high demand for electricity and strong grid in New York and Taiwan, which can absorb the large scale offshore wind power, require less action for route to markets, wind dispatch down resolution and power to gas, than in Ireland

Following issues identified in the case studies, the recommended future scope of work for WP6 should include national and international clusters for supply chain, region-based REFiT and incentives, routes to transport and heat markets and storage of hydrogen, and cumulative impact assessment.

Lessons learned indicate that consideration of spatial and temporal scales are essential in developing the blueprint for sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland. A three-dimensional template is therefore proposed for correlating and analysing the information from each work package in EirWind, as an approach to synthesising the research, and for the development of a blueprint as the final project output. It will loop over results and recommendations including wind resources, data, ports and logistics, stakeholder groups, and grid to populate the template. The approach will provide a whole of Ireland view, as well as a separate analysis for the East Coast, South Coast, and West Coast, integrated with the GIS datasets and maps. As a next step, development scenarios for an agreed timeline, (e.g. 2025, 2035, 2040 and 2050), should be discussed and agreed with the Consortium.

List of Abbreviations

AoA - Area of Analysis

BOEM - Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (U.S.)

GW - gigawatts

NYSERDA - New York State Energy Research and Development Authority

OWT – Offshore wind turbine

PPA - Power purchase agreements

WTIV - Wind turbine installation vessel

Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	5
2	Description of Work Package 6 and this deliverable.....	6
3	Case Study Review.....	6
3.1	The New York State Offshore Wind Blueprint and Master Plan	7
3.1.1	Background.....	7
3.1.2	Blueprint for the New York State Offshore Wind Master Plan	8
3.1.3	New York State Offshore Wind Master Plan	12
3.2	The Vision for the Offshore Wind Supply Chain in Virginia, U.S.	13
3.2.1	Background.....	13
3.2.2	Roadmap to offshore wind development and supply chain	14
3.3	Offshore Wind Development in Taiwan.....	16
3.3.1	Background.....	16
3.3.2	Government’s promotion targets, strategies and incentives	17
3.4	Comparison of three case studies	19
4	A proposed 3-D template of the blueprint for sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland	20
4.1	Background.....	20
4.2	Objectives and approach.....	20
5	Recommendations	22
	References.....	23

1 Introduction

Ireland's sea area is around ten times the size of its landmass, at circa 100,000 km², and the country has one of the best offshore renewable energy resources in the world. This offers significant potential for offshore wind, wave and tidal energy. Ireland's Offshore Renewable Energy Development Plan (OREDPA) [1] indicates that the total amount of offshore wind farm development is 34.8 GW – 39 GW without likely significant adverse effects on the environment. Ireland clearly has a unique position with offshore wind, including an opportunity to become an early leader in the emerging floating wind energy market. However, with only 25 MW of offshore wind power operating in Ireland, offshore wind clearly has not been prioritised up until now. This development lacuna has prevailed while onshore wind projects have mushroomed, along with community concerns and controversy over planning issues. Progress in offshore wind has been hindered to date by the cost of technology, consenting, and the level of subsidy required. With improvements in technology and reductions in cost, the sector is at a new point of departure in Ireland.

Given a number of facts (i) the high potential and unique position of offshore wind in Ireland, (ii) recent advancement and cost reduction in offshore wind technology, (iii) lowest lifecycle CO₂ emission of offshore wind energy, (iv) the ambitious targets of the Climate Action Plan [2], (v) large shares of fossil fuels in transport and heat sectors, and (vi) large and increasing greenhouse emissions from energy and transport sectors, the opportunities for offshore wind in Ireland is significant. The question is how to turn the opportunities into reality.

This question can be answered by a blueprint for sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland. The Eirwind Blueprint report should be a landmark report, based on comprehensive synthesis of the Eirwind research. The Blueprint should analyse the current state of play for offshore wind, and offer guidance on its future development. The development of subsequent masterplans, spatial plans, or guidelines are the prerogative of policy-makers. The Blueprint recommendations to government and industry should be pragmatic and actionable, making it possible to take full advantage of increasing momentum within the sector.

The aim of this report is to take stock of existing approaches to developing blueprints, masterplans or visions, for offshore wind, with a view to informing a methodology for achieving research synthesis in WP6, that will achieve a Blueprint with the key characteristics outlined above. The document commences with a statement of targets for WP6, analysis and insights from select case studies, and recommendations for WP6, for review by the Eirwind consortium.

2 Description of Work Package 6 and this deliverable

The objectives of this work package are to [3]:

- Consider the opportunity around the sustainable development of Ireland's marine resources, using offshore wind as the catalyst for innovation and impact.
- Develop and implement an iterative communications and dissemination strategy for the project.
- Look beyond the project, and make recommendations for future industry-led research collaboration.

The work package aims to evaluate the **benefits and the potential bottlenecks** for concomitant development of offshore wind with mariculture, fisheries, wave energy and other spatial activities, from a spatial planning perspective. It will do this by looking beyond the scale of individual study areas to extrapolate conclusions and lessons learned from WP2 to WP5. The overall synthesis of WP2 to WP5 will lead to a blueprint for the sustainable/spatial development of offshore wind in Ireland.

An iterative process of synthesising outputs from WP2 – WP5, will be used for communication and dissemination of project results to targeted audiences and end users. This deliverable presents the review of the offshore wind masterplans available from other countries to identify relevant approaches and compare gaps. The methodology for the phased approach to synthesis will be discussed with the Consortium.

3 Case Study Review

The three case studies presented below have been selected to represent a diverse range of strategic processes and plans, each of which provides unique insights for WP6. Justification for their individual selection is as follows: -

The New York master planning process, which was preceded by a Blueprint, provides a useful checklist of the range of studies and stakeholder engagement processes, that can be used to inform a strategic plan. The New York case study also reveals the core tenants to realising an ambitious programme of development, which needs to be considered in an Irish context, to give effect to the government target of 3.5GW of offshore wind by 2030.

The visioning process in Virginia provides insights to the potential benefits of regional clusters in developing supply chain opportunities. This is useful in an Irish context, as recognised by Enterprise Ireland, in seeking bilateral opportunities with the UK. Virginia is also interesting as it seeks to catch up with progress in other east coast states, not dissimilar to the gap that needs to be closed, between Ireland and other European Member States. Finally, the approach in Virginia has been to focus on unique selling points, with a strong 'open for business' message attached.

Taiwan was selected as a case study because of similarities with Ireland, in terms of geography, development level, energy mix and the high dependency on energy imports.

3.1 The New York State Offshore Wind Blueprint and Master Plan

3.1.1 Background

The New York annual electric energy usage decreased 0.23% annually in 10 years from 2007 to 2017 [4] and slightly increased in 2018 as in Figure 3-1. The New York Independent System Operator (NYISO) forecasts that energy use in New York — including the impacts of energy efficiency and customer-based Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) — will decrease annually by an average rate of 0.14% from 2018 through 2028 (Figure 3-2).

New York has a relatively diverse mix of generation resources, from a statewide perspective [5, p. 25]. As shown in Figure 3-3, its largest contribution in 2018 from dual fuel (gas/oil, 34%), nuclear power (32%), hydro power (21%) and only 3% from wind. It should be noted that by 2029, more than 8,370 MW of gas turbine and steam-turbine generating capacity in New York could reach an age at which nationally 95% of these types of generation capacity have deactivated [5, p. 16]. That fleet of fossil fuel-fired power plants includes older facilities with higher operating expenses or fuel costs, which are typically selected to run only during periods of higher demand or when market clearing prices are higher [5, p. 25]. Renewable resources have no fuel costs and low emissions and are more competitive than older and potentially less efficient fossil generators.

Figure 3-1: Annual Electric Energy Usage Trends in New York State: 2000-2018 [5]

Figure 3-2: Electric Energy Usage Trends and Forecast in New York State: 2018-2029 [5]

Figure 3-3: Electric Energy Production in New York State by Fuel Source in 2018 [5]

New York has 39 GW of clean, wind-driven energy potential off its Atlantic coast—enough to power approximately 15 million homes [6]. It also has the potential to serve as a new, local source of affordable power for the New York City metropolitan area and Long Island, where energy demand and prices are high and there are significant opportunities to increase renewable energy generation, particularly through the use of offshore wind. Like all energy resources, offshore wind must be developed responsibly [7] [8]

The present sequential process of developing an offshore wind project in the U.S. involves the following steps [7]:

- Securing a wind energy area lease from the U.S. Department of Interior’s Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (BOEM).
- Conducting an environmental assessment to study the effects of a measurement campaign to assess wind speeds, wave heights, seabed conditions, wildlife presence, and other characteristics of the site.
- Once environmental assessment has been approved, carrying out site assessment, that can take several years.
- Developing construction and operations plans for the wind project, after sufficient site data is collected from site assessment.
- BOEM carry out an environmental impact study that typically takes over a year and has multiple opportunities for stakeholder input.
- Securing agreements for purchasing the electricity, financing, and plans for interconnecting to the grid.
- Only after approval of the construction and operations plan, as well as all State and other required approvals and agreements, the project may start construction.

Offshore wind development in the U.S. requires two distinct and de-coupled actions: acquiring a site lease that allows for project development on federal underwater estates, and securing an agreement for power purchase [7]. This creates substantial risk for developers who pursue leasing at great financial risk and uncertainty without the stability of power purchase agreements. Consequently, that risk reduces efficiency of development efforts and increases overall project cost. The Master Plan [9] therefore joins these two critical elements, with a focus on reducing development risk, lowering costs, and enabling the greatest possible benefit to the State. It adopts approaches that improve the speed, cost, and effectiveness of the development process in a manner that fully considers environmental, maritime, and societal issues, resulting in a fully balanced evaluation and identification of potential offshore wind sites.

3.1.2 Blueprint for the New York State Offshore Wind Master Plan

The process to develop the Master Plan was outlined in the Blueprint for the New York State Offshore Wind Master Plan (thereafter called the ‘**Blueprint**’). The Blueprint described how stakeholder input and feedback would be pursued to inform the Master Plan. The blueprint activities launched in the fall of 2016 by the New York State Energy Research and Development Authority (NYSERDA), with contributions from Department of Environmental Conservation, Department of Labor, Department of

Public Service, Empire State Development, the Long Island Power Authority, the New York Power Authority, and the Office of Parks, Recreation and Historic Preservation, and concluded with a completed Master Plan by the end of 2017. The Master Plan is being updated annually thereafter.

The New York State Offshore Wind Master Plan covers a 16,740-square-mile (43,356-square kilometre) area of ocean for potential future sites for offshore wind. It outlines priority actions for achieving a target of 2,400 MW of offshore wind by 2030, enough to power 1.2 million homes, serving New York City and Long Island.

The masterplan was preceded by the publication of twenty site, grid and economic studies, and plans for stakeholder engagement. The main components of these studies and approaches are summarised below.

Site, Grid, and Economic Studies

Costs have been a major decision making factor for offshore wind development and are ultimately embedded in the power prices that consumers pay. Defining a pipeline of offshore wind projects in the Master Plan would therefore create a visible market that helps attract supply chain investments and reduce the cost of offshore wind energy to consumers. That defining process required information arising from studies concerned with Site Assessment and Characterization, Grid and Interconnection, and Economics and Cost-Effectiveness.

[Site Assessment and Characterization](#)

Substantial risks and costs are incurred in the early development and permitting processes. In order to reduce these risks and costs, the State has committed to undertaking pre-development activities, including resource assessment, baseline environment studies, and site characterization [7].

- *Partner Engagement*: To form a **market advisory group** comprised of key industry experts who can actively inform and contribute to the site assessment and characterization. Through active engagement with that group, any detailed analyses could be ensured to be completed in a manner that is suitable for project financing and construction.
- *Site Assessment Data Campaign*: to measure meteorological data such as the speed and direction of the wind and the height of waves in the ocean using technology deployed in one or more locations in the Study Area.
- *Site Characterization Data Campaign*: to map seabed and sub-seabed conditions, sample seabed soil, detect geohazards, and locate existing cables and underwater structures.

[Grid and Interconnection](#)

- *Partner Engagement*: to work with the New York Independent System Operator, DPS, NYPA, LIPA, Con Edison, other electricity providers and grid operators, and offshore electrical component suppliers to undertake interconnection studies and analysis.
- *Offshore Wind Interconnection Study*: to conduct detailed analyses of options and costs of injecting offshore wind into various interconnection points in load of the New York grid, as well as any required transmission upgrades for distribution and reliability.

- *Cumulative/Regional Impact Analysis:* to consider the interaction of New York State's development activities with those of other Northeastern and Mid-Atlantic states and the cumulative impact of developing large amounts of offshore wind to determine the impact to the State's grid and electric market.
- *Transmission Cost Study:* to evaluate the cost of offshore wind transmission and required grid upgrades associated with offshore wind that benefit New York State ratepayers and align with the State's market structures.
- *Transmission Siting Proceedings:* to work closely to assess the need for transmission proceedings and to fully consider ratepayer costs and benefits.

Economics and Cost-Effectiveness

- *Partner Engagement:* to work closely with the market advisory group to design Clean Energy Standard procurement and contracting approaches to best support offshore wind for New York State at scale in a manner that fully considers ratepayer costs and benefits.
- *Offtake Mechanisms and Value Modelling:* to analyze options for economic arrangements for the State to support energy offtake agreements for offshore wind projects that optimize the value to ratepayers.
- *Cost Reduction Pathways:* to conduct an analysis of the impact on costs due to new and emerging technologies, new and improved installation methods, and potential State actions that can reduce costs.
- *Offshore Wind Quantities:* to conduct analyses to quantify the quantity and timing of planned offshore wind resources solicited through the Clean Energy Standard.
- *Evaluation:* to evaluate existing and potential local load and congestion points where the value of offshore wind is such that it is competitive with other generation and transmission solutions.
- *Additional Wind Energy Area (WEA) Identification:* to initiate a process with BOEM to identify further WEAs that are best suited for development in quantities to meet the State's offshore wind demand.
- *Offshore Wind Vessel Assessment:* to conduct an assessment of installation, operations, and maintenance vessels requirements (including the Jones Act) and costs.

Seeking Input from Stakeholders

In order to inform future projects and turbine siting to minimize potential project impacts, specific needs and actions needed to be determined. The anticipated approaches associated with key stakeholder groups in New York State and State, federal, and local agencies were therefore outlined as follows [7].

Coastal Communities

- *Outreach:* to engage local communities, tribal nations, and other interested stakeholders and demonstrate the potential visibility of wind turbines under different lighting and visibility scenarios in offshore areas considered for development.
- *Assessments and Surveys:* to conduct historic and cultural resource assessments and archaeological surveys of potential historic sites of cultural significance, including submerged

and onshore resources, to determine impacts of potential offshore wind sites and, where appropriate, present mitigation strategies.

- *Lighting Impacts:* to research and propose ways to reduce or eliminate adverse visual impacts from aviation and navigational lighting.

Environmental Groups:

- *Outreach:* to engage federal agencies, environmental groups, and experts with respect to environmental concerns and potential mitigation methods for all aspects of offshore wind development, construction, and operations.
- *Wildlife Surveys:* to undertake surveys of marine and avian species to measure and monitor the seasonal presence, distribution and abundance, and migration patterns to better understand the wildlife present offshore and to create a baseline to measure the impact of offshore wind projects.
- *Seabed Studies:* to undertake studies of the seabed to assess potential impacts on currents, sediment transport, turbidity, and the construction of subsea structures on marine species habitats.
- *Develop Guidelines:* to work with DOS, DEC, federal agencies, environmental groups and experts to develop best practices for the development of offshore wind resources off the coast of New York State. These best practices will include siting, construction, and operating requirements to minimize the risks to fish and wildlife.

Maritime and Fishing Communities

- *Outreach:* to engage the maritime and fishing communities, including out-of-state operators, that operate in the Study Area, that includes consulting with:
 - The U.S. Coast Guard and vessel operators to determine how they manoeuvre in the vicinity of other vessels and fixed objects, and
 - The fishing industry regarding the location, timing, and frequency of their use of significant fishing grounds and the gear used in the offshore planning area; the levels of fishing effort and landings from the offshore planning area; habitat features and environmental conditions that may serve as proxies for favorable fishing conditions; and persistent or emerging trends.
- *Marine Navigation Study:* to work with the U.S. Coast Guard, the Port Authorities, and BOEM to conduct an in-depth analysis of ship traffic data and probabilistic risk analysis for vessels operating in the vicinity of potential offshore wind energy areas and determine mitigation actions such as turbine placement and lighting to reduce identified risks.
- *Fisheries Assessment:* to evaluate fishing areas, potential displacement and changes in fishing effort, and potential economic impacts resulting from offshore wind development.
- *Guidelines Development:* to work with DOS, DEC, DPS, the U.S. Coast Guard and BOEM to develop best practices for siting offshore wind farms, including turbine layouts and spacing, cable burial details, and construction operations, to minimize the impacts on the maritime and fishing industries

Local Economic Stakeholders

- *Outreach*: to engage trade unions, ports, and manufacturing hubs throughout the State to gather information to inform workforce development initiatives. That include consulting with port officials regarding how to maximize the potential for offshore wind economic development opportunities related to maritime trades, particularly the need for skilled labour and for onshore facilities for assembling project components prior to installation.
- *Supply Chain Assessment*: to analyze the supply chain and infrastructure needs of offshore wind to identify gaps in the current New York State supply chain that can be developed in a manner that will reduce costs for the industry and increase the value of economic development from offshore wind, including port facility improvements.
- *Workforce Development Study*: to assess the current regional workforce to identify potential gaps in skilled labour and provide recommendations for workforce training or advanced degree programs to fill those gaps.

The blueprint gaps including less actions for route to markets, wind dispatch down resolution and power to gas should be noted and understood because the high demand in electricity and strong grid in New York [10] those can absorb the large scale offshore wind power.

3.1.3 New York State Offshore Wind Master Plan

The master plan developed following the blueprint describes the objectives and methodology of the New York State's planning process, and identifies the 20 studies the State undertook to gather data on environmental, social, economic, regulatory, and infrastructure issues relevant to offshore wind energy development [9]. The master plan also reviews the State's extensive outreach efforts with interested agencies, entities, communities, and individuals, which helped achieve a balanced evaluation of the potential for offshore wind development. It sets forth the State's comprehensive strategy to reach that goal, and specifically [9]:

- Identifies the most favorable areas for potential offshore wind energy development
- Describes the economic and environmental benefits of offshore wind energy development
- Addresses mechanisms to procure offshore wind energy at the lowest ratepayer cost
- Analyzes costs and cost-reduction pathways
- Recommends measures to mitigate potential impacts of offshore wind energy development
- Identifies infrastructure requirements and assesses existing facilities
- Identifies workforce opportunities

The master plan process has been and will continue to be a joint effort of the NYSERDA, the New York State Department of Environmental Conservation, the New York State Department of Labor, the New York State Department of State, the New York State Department of Public Service, the New York State Office of Parks, Recreation and Historic Preservation, Empire State Development, the Long Island Power Authority, and the New York Power Authority.

The master plan is supported by a suite of 20 appended studies listed below those provide a body of information concerning a variety of environmental, social, economic, regulatory, and infrastructure-related issues implicated in planning for future offshore wind energy development. Decision making with respect to each of the 20 studies began with an assessment of a 43,356-square kilometer offshore study area in the Atlantic Ocean, which extends from New York City and the south shore of Long Island to beyond the continental shelf break and slope. For each particular topic of study, the State team refined the offshore study area into a larger or smaller Area of Analysis based on study-specific factors or stakeholder and public input [9].

- 1) Analysis of Multibeam Echo Sounder (MBES) and Benthic Survey Data [11].
- 2) Assessment of Ports and Infrastructure [12].
- 3) Aviation and Radar Assets Study [13].
- 4) Birds and Bats Study [14]. This
- 5) Cable Landfall Permitting Study [15].
- 6) Cables, Pipelines, and Other Infrastructure [16].
- 7) Consideration of Potential Cumulative Effects [17].
- 8) Cultural Resources Study [18].
- 9) Environmental Sensitivity Analysis [19].
- 10) Fish and Fisheries Study [20].
- 11) Health and Safety Study [21].
- 12) Marine Mammals and Sea Turtles Study [22].
- 13) Marine Recreational Uses Study [23].
- 14) Offshore Wind Injection Assessment [10].
- 15) Preliminary Offshore Wind Resource Assessment [24].
- 16) Sand and Gravel Resources Study [25].
- 17) Shipping and Navigation Study [26].
- 18) U.S. Jones Act Compliant Offshore Wind Turbine Installation Vessel Study [27].
- 19) Visibility Threshold Study [28].
- 20) The Workforce Opportunity of Offshore Wind in New York [29].

3.2 The Vision for the Offshore Wind Supply Chain in Virginia, U.S.

3.2.1 Background

Coal is the primary energy resource produced in Virginia. Almost two-thirds of Virginia is forested, and the state's widely distributed forests hold abundant biomass potential. Energy consumption in the state is supplied major source including natural gas, motor gasoline, nuclear and inter-state electricity, as shown in [Figure 3-4](#). It should be noted that energy consumption in Virginia is **more than two and a**

half times greater than the state's energy production [30]. The transportation sector is the largest end-use energy-consuming sector in the state. Virginia has the third-largest state-maintained transportation network in the nation, including six major interstate highways. The transportation, commercial, and residential sectors each consume much more energy than the state's industrial sector, and Virginia's per capita total energy consumption is below the national average. Virginia trails behind other east coast states such as New York, Massachusetts, Rhode Island and New Jersey, in planning for the development of offshore wind.

Figure 3-4: Energy consumption in Virginia in 2018 [31]

3.2.2 Roadmap to offshore wind development and supply chain

In 2018, the Department of Mines, Minerals and Energy (DMME), solicited a partnership with BVG Associates, to produce a vision for the sector, to help unlock Virginia's offshore wind potential. The resulting vision identifies Virginia's potential to become a national leader in the emerging U.S. offshore wind industry within the next decade [32]. Excellent port infrastructure and geographical advantages provide Virginia, not only with a path to meeting the state's goal of developing giga-watts of renewable energy, but also an opportunity to establish the state as a hub for the East Coast offshore wind supply chain (Figure 3-5). Virginia is well positioned to derive economic benefit by establishing a supply chain while growing the industrial base at this early stage will prepare Virginia to competitively deliver its own 2GW in the coming years [33]. The visioning process focused on the identification of five main competitive advantages of the State are [32]:

1. Industrial coastal infrastructure, with large areas for lay-down and storage, quayside length for load-out, and direct access to the open ocean with unlimited vertical clearance.
2. A large skilled and experienced workforce in shipbuilding and ship repair, ports, logistics and vessel operations.
3. Highway, rail, and inland waterway connections linking Virginia's ports to industrial centres throughout the Southeast, Mid-Atlantic, and Midwest.
4. Eastern population centres with high and growing electricity demand, particularly for the internet economy. Northern Virginia is hosting a major and growing internet corridor, and in Virginia Beach, two new data centres are being built.

5. High-voltage interconnection capability in Virginia Beach, sufficient for all the anticipated commercial lease area capacity after moderate investment.

Figure 3-5: Projected market share in installed capacity for each East Coast State in the period 2016-2030 [33]

A collaborative multi-state cluster concept – the “Mid and South Atlantic Coast supply cluster” has been developed in support of the view that regional collaboration will deliver the most effective offshore wind supply chain [33]. This multi-state industrial base, aligned with logistics benefits and workforce synergies in each area, will attract anchor tenants and lead toward a supply chain diversity, delivering the best economic benefit. Manufacturing offshore wind components and offering offshore wind services in Virginia and other neighbouring states will, once at scale, enable multiple offshore wind competitors to reach substantial cost savings. In order to implement that concept, the following recommendations have been made [33]:

- Create a “Virginia Office for Offshore Wind” to provide a clearinghouse and facilitator to advance offshore wind. This office would coordinate stakeholder collaboration, serve as point-of-contact for offshore wind activities, support both offshore wind prospects and businesses within the regional cluster, and focus on aligning needs with regional business capacity.
- Work toward a multi-state regional supply chain cluster, offering the industry a wide network and the best of what each state has to offer. That includes working with other states on their core strengths and help secure business opportunities for regional state partners. This also requires collective engagement with the offshore wind industry to understand supply needs/preferences to help facilitate a 'best fit' scenario.
- Solicit and attract "anchor tenant" suppliers, with a focus on major components. That includes sending a strong “open for business” message, addressing areas of interest and concern and reinforcing through commitment of local and state decision-makers.
- Enable and grow Virginia’s business opportunity through partnerships and infrastructure.
- Grow Virginia business opportunity through workforce development.

3.3 Offshore Wind Development in Taiwan

3.3.1 Background

The population of Taiwan in 2018 was 23.6 million. The country’s power generation in 2016 depended 46% on coal, 12% on nuclear, 4% on oil, 32% on natural gas and only 6% on renewable sources, as depicted in Figure 3-6 . In 2025, Taiwan aims to be nuclear-free and rely less on coal, while boosting renewable energy and natural gas [34]. There are good offshore wind resources in Taiwanese shallow water (5 – 20 m), deep water (20 – 50m) and waters deeper than 50, as in Figure 3-7.

Figure 3-6: Power general mix in Taiwan in 2016 and goals in 2025 [34]

Shallow Water (5-20 m):

- Area: 1,779.2 km2
- Potential: 9 GW
- Feasible: 1.2 GW

Deep Water (20-50 m):

- Area: 6,547 km2
- Potential: 48 GW
- Feasible: 5 GW

Deeper Water (> 50 m):

- Potential: 90 GW
- Feasible: 9 GW

Figure 3-7: Taiwan offshore wind potential [35]

3.3.2 Government’s promotion targets, strategies and incentives

In order to promote offshore wind development, the government of Taiwan set up the national "Thousand Wind Turbines" Project [36] in 2012. The project objectives are to complete development and establishment of the nation's first offshore wind farm by 2015, to complete a 520MW shallow-water wind farm in 2020, and to install about 800 offshore wind turbines (4,000MW), and 450 onshore wind turbines (1,200MW) prior to 2030 to ultimately deliver a total of more than 1000 wind turbines, and a total installed capacity of 5200 MW, as demonstrated in **Figure 3-8**. It should be noted that the targets for 2025 and 2030 in **Figure 3-8** have been progressively updated from the previous figures for offshore wind: 1,800 MW in 2025 and 3,000 MW in 2030 [35].

Figure 3-8: Updated scaled roadmap of the “Thousand Wind Turbines” Project in Taiwan [36].

Figure 3-9: Organizational operation of the “Thousand Wind Turbines” Project [36].

The "Thousand Wind Turbines Project Promotion Office" was established to perform related tasks, in which, the Bureau of Energy (BOE) and Ministry of Economic Affairs (MOEA) actively pursued deployment of the project right after the approval. Furthermore, the "BOE, MOEA Renewable Energy 4-in-1 Promotion Office" was established by integrating related promotion offices for the purpose of fully cooperating with government policies [36]. The Office core missions are:- coordinating regulations and administrative obstacles, promoting an offshore demonstration plan, assisting the industry to enhance technology, and promoting domestic industrial development. The Office operational

hierarchy in [Figure 3-9](#) shows that their focuses are both policy planning and promotion, and technology R&D and promotion.

Table 3-1 lists the current and previous Feed-in Tariff for wind energy in Taiwan. However, the subsidy on capital costs is not attractive enough for investors and the current FIT subsidy is applied equally for all regions of Taiwan, regardless of the distinct conditions of each region [37]. A more appropriate subsidy for capital costs, and regional FIT subsidy to cater for regional variability, has been proposed to promote the expansion of offshore wind systems [37].

Table 3-1: Feed-in Tariff for wind energy in Taiwan

	In 2013, per kWh	In 2017, per kWh
Onshore wind	NT\$2.6258 (€6.73c) [35]	NT\$2.8776(€8.20c) for 20 years [36]
Offshore wind	NT\$5.5626 (€14.26c) [35]	NT\$6.0437(€17.20c) for 20 years [36]

Demonstration Incentives

The Offshore Wind Power Demonstration Incentive Program was formulated to encourage the industry to build offshore demonstration wind farms. The government provided a subsidy for 50% installation expenditures of the four offshore demonstration wind turbines [36]:

- Demonstration Wind Farm: Water depth above 5 m; the site is determined by the applicant, and the total installed capacity should be more than 100 MW but not exceeding 200 MW.
- Demonstration Wind Turbines: Each case includes 2 offshore wind power systems, and each wind turbine is required to generate a capacity of more than 3 MW.
- Incentive Fees:
 - For installation: The upper limit shall be 50% of the installation expenditures based on the offshore wind power initial phase of the year when the Program was promulgated, and shall not exceed 50% of the total expenditures of installed demonstration wind turbines.
 - For operations: The upper limit shall be NT\$250 millions (approximately €7.2 millions)

Technology Gaps [35]:

- Turbine design resistant to typhoons
- Foundation design resistant to earthquakes
- Migrating birds & ocean mammals
- Local fishery, navigation and harbour development
- Risk assessment and mitigation
- Vessel coordination and construction scheduling

3.4 Comparison of three case studies

In order to maximise the lessons learnt from the developed blueprints, masterplans, visions and policies in the reviewed case studies in to methodology and development of a blueprint for the offshore wind master plan in Ireland, a comparison of three case studies is given in **Table 3-2**. The target and in-charge organisations, aspects different from Ireland, and unique aspects relevant to Ireland and the EirWind project have been captured and compared that emphasises the need for a blueprint.

Table 3-2: Comparison of three case studies

Reviewed Case Study	Target (Scale, timeline), in-charge organisation	Aspect different from Ireland	Unique aspect relevant to Ireland/EirWind
Blueprint and Master Plan for the New York State Offshore Wind	2,400MW by 2030, by New York State Energy Research and Development Authority (NYSERDA), with contributions from other state departments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extremely high but slightly decreasing volume of demand in electricity. Backup/balancing generation available Present low penetration of renewable electricity Strong coordination of NYSERDA and support policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sequential process of developing an offshore wind project. Components and approaches of the blueprint, particularly Site, Grid, and Economic Studies; and Seeking Input from Stakeholders, for the master plan Goals and 20 supporting studies/documents of the master plan
Vision for the Offshore Wind Supply Chain in Virginia, U.S	2GW in 2025 – 2030; Hub for the East Coast offshore wind supply chain; BVG Associates, solicited by Department of Mines, Minerals and Energy (DMME)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Infrastructures (ports, etc.) Major energy supply mix: natural gas, motor gasoline, nuclear and inter-state electricity Present low penetration of renewable electricity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Issue of energy security (energy consumption in Virginia is more than 2.5 times greater than the production) Virginia Office for Offshore Wind to provide a clearinghouse and facilitator to advance offshore wind Cluster: hub for the East Coast offshore wind supply chain Roadmap for offshore wind supply chain
Offshore Wind Development in Taiwan	520MW in shallow-water in 2020; 800 turbines (4,000MW) prior to 2030 By Bureau of Energy (BOE) and Ministry of Economic Affairs (MOEA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High demand in energy (population of 23.6 million in 2018) Readiness of technology and supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High potential offshore wind High potential in deep water (90 GW) with 9GW feasible. Nuclear power free in 2025 Clear roadmap/master plan for offshore wind Meaningful name "Thousand Wind Turbines" of the Project Subsidy policies Demonstration Incentives

4 A proposed 3-D template of the blueprint for sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland

4.1 Background

There is a need to consider the spatial and temporal scales for a variety of issues in developing the blueprint for sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland, as a result of the mismatch between the timelines for the realisation of critical infrastructure and markets, as well as the wide ranging characteristics of project development in the east, versus the south and west coasts, - all of which will have major implications for how offshore wind develops in Ireland. :

- The challenges in markets and limit in electricity grid and energy transmission networks those are difficult to absorb large scale (GW) deployment of offshore wind energy as featured in the Grid-MSP Workshop Public Report [38].
- More than 70% of offshore wind potential in Ireland is floating offshore wind locating in the South and West coasts [1] [39], in which the costs are still high and not yet at commercial scale. Moreover, there have been no floating wind demonstration project existing in Ireland.
- Offshore wind farms will be developed in the East coast, then in the South Coast, and finally the West coast [39] due to water depths, available technology, capacity and development of the grid.
- Penetrating the transport and heat markets takes time because of the gaps in the development of domestic technology, infrastructure capacity and support policy for converting offshore wind power to other types of energy including hydrogen and power to gas [40] [38].

4.2 Objectives and approach

In order to meet the need, a three-dimensional (3-D) template is therefore proposed in **Table 4-1** for correlating and analysing the information from each WP for the development of a blueprint for offshore wind development in Ireland. It will:

- Loop over results, findings, and recommendations including wind resources, data, ports and logistics, stakeholder groups, grid to populate the template.
- Analyse iteratively the cumulative effects based on the set of criteria and the filled templates.
- Be separate for the East Coast, South Coast, and West Coast.
- Be integrated with the GIS datasets/maps resulted from WP2

Other results/recommendations independent of scale such as stakeholder engagement can be correlated in 2-D templates.

Table 4-1: A proposed 3-D template of the blueprint for sustainable development of offshore wind in the East Coast/South Coast/West Coast of Ireland

Sector	Time	2020	2025	2030	2035	2050
	Scale (Total installation)	25 MW	?	?	?	?
Site, data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement and gaps • Data availability • Future survey plans 						
Biology & Environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPA • Seabird vulnerability maps • Effects on marine mammals • Measure to the effects 						
Governance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy development • Job creation 						
Optimised offshore technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technologies • Cost 						
Energy market & infrastructure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grid development plan • Cost, benefit, & risk • Demonstration projects 						

Based on the wind energy roadmap [41] as in [Figure 4-1](#), the scales of offshore wind installation in 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, 2045 and 2050 are approximately 1GW, 4GW, 9GW, 14GW, 25GW and 26GW, respectively. However, given that this publication was well before the advancement of offshore wind technology, particularly floating wind, these scale figures need to be revisited.

Figure 4-1: Cumulative installations with repowering of onshore and offshore wind to 2050 [41]

5 Recommendations

Within the present scope of work, in order to best integrate and leverage the results and recommendations from individual deliverables and work packages, and to facilitate the development of an effective blueprint for offshore wind energy in Ireland, the following points are recommended to be considered by the EirWind Consortium:

- Consideration of spatial and temporal scale(where relevant) while implementing individual deliverables and work package.
- Consider the target and in-charge organisations, aspects different from Ireland, and unique aspects relevant to Ireland of three case studies presented in **Table 3-2**.
- Discuss and agree on the development scales for 2025, 2030, .., 2050 to be filled in **Table 4-1**
- Discuss and agree the actions to follow up with development scales.

For the future scope of work of the project, the following points are recommended to be considered:

- The actions in the Blueprint for the New York State Offshore Wind Master Plan [7]. However, the gaps including less actions for route to markets, wind dispatch down and power to gas should be noted and understood because the high demand in electricity and strong grid in New York those can absorb large scale offshore wind power.
- National and international clusters for supply chain in offshore wind energy, offshore engineering and maritime [33].
- Tariff, incentive and support based on regions [37].
- Route to market: transportation and heat, where hydrogen is one of the key links.
- Cumulative impact assessment: it was carried out in the New York offshore wind master plan by using geographic scope, the value and sensitivity of the environmental, cultural, and socioeconomic resources, and the duration of the impacts [42]. The cumulative effects criteria were applied only to the resources carried forward as a result of the potentially minor or greater impacts.

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